

An Analysis of Investors' Mindset in Selecting the Schemes of Mutual Fund

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Abstract— Mutual funds have come as a much needed help to small investors who face a lot of problems in the share market, limited resources, lack of professional advice, lack of information, etc. Mutual funds offer different schemes to meet varied needs of investors. Some schemes offer regular income, some offer a promise of capital appreciation, some offer greater liquidity. Growth in gross domestic savings and increasing equity cult in the country along with desire in the people to earn from savings has led to the rapid growth of mutual funds. Savings pattern of people has also changed from bank deposits to mutual funds. People have started looking for well managed mutual funds to accumulate more wealth over the years. An investor takes into account various factors while deciding about buying of a mutual fund. These ranges of factors begin with investor perception, the promised return and to the attractiveness of the offer. The investors look for safety first in mutual fund products followed by good returns, tax benefits, capital appreciation and liquidity. An investor takes into account various factors while deciding about buying of a mutual fund. These ranges of factors begin with investor perception, the promised return and to the attractiveness of the offer. The objective of this paper is to highlight the various factors which influence the selection of mutual funds by retail investors. We can say that while selecting any one of the schemes of the mutual fund, the investor must bear in mind his age and the capacity to bear risk. Investor must also ensure that the management of the fund has a market reputation of being more transparent and the perception of an honest and efficient management. Investor must also examine the consistency in the performance and the after sales services of the mutual fund. The present paper highlights the various types of mutual funds introduced by various fund managers. The present paper brought out the various merits and limitations in investing in mutual funds.

Index Terms—Mutual Fund, Fund Manager, Close Ended, Open Ended

I. INTRODUCTION

It's no more diamonds or gold that are the vogue when it comes to present a gift to your daughter's wedding or son's birthday. With more and more Indians dabbling on the bourses, the traditional items have now made way for mutual funds and shares. Call it the wide-spread financial awareness

or the increase in investment appetite but Indians are now getting comfortable with giving and receiving shares and mutual funds as gifts.

The concept of mutual fund in India is not a new one. It started in India with the introduction of UTI in 1964. Since then it has developed a lot especially in the beginning of the last decade of 20th century. The genesis of mutual fund is associated with the Society General de Belgique established in 1882 in Belgium. After this the mutual funds came up in UK and USA followed by other nations. In India this concept came in 1964.

Mutual funds have emerged as an important segment of financial markets in India, especially following the initiatives taken by Government in the 2000 budget to resolve problems associated with UTI's US 64 Scheme and to liberalize tax treatment of incomes earned through mutual funds. They now play a crucial role in channelising savings of millions of individuals from different parts of the country into investment in both equity and debt instruments. Currently, the mutual fund penetration in India is around 4.8 percent and a study on the Indian mutual fund industry by the Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India (ASSOCHAM) states that the mutual fund industry may end up notching assets of about Rs. 6 trillion by March 2008.

Mutual fund is a mechanism for pooling the resources by issuing units to the investors and investing funds in securities in accordance with objectives as disclosed in offer document. Investments in securities are spread across a wide cross-section of industries and sectors and thus the risk is reduced. Diversification reduces the risk because all stocks may not move in the same direction in the same proportion at the same time. Mutual fund issues units to the investors in accordance with quantum of money invested by them. Investors of mutual funds are known as unit holders. The profits and losses are shared by the investors in proportion to their investments.

HISTORY OF MUTUAL FUNDS

The history of mutual funds in India can be divided into four distinct phases which are summarized below:

First Phase (1964-87)

Unit Trust of India was established in 1963 by an Act of Parliament. It was set up by the RBI and functioned under the regulatory and administrative control of the RBI. In 1978, UTI was de-linked from the RBI and the IDBI took over the regulatory and administrative control in place of RBI. The first scheme launched by UTI was Unit Scheme 1964.

Second Phase (1987-1993)

1987 was the year which marked the entry of non UTI, public sector mutual funds set by public sector banks and Life Insurance Corporation of India and General Insurance Corporation of India. SBI Mutual Fund was the first one to be established in June 1987 followed by Canbank Mutual Fund, PNB Mutual Fund, Indian Bank Mutual Fund, Bank of India Mutual Fund, BOB Mutual Fund. LIC established its mutual fund in June 1989 while GIC had set up its mutual fund in December 1990.

Third Phase (1993-2003)

A new era started in the Indian mutual fund industry with the entry of private sector funds in 1993, giving the Indian investors a wider choice of fund families. The erstwhile Kothari Pioneer (now merged with Franklin Templeton) was the first private sector mutual fund registered in July 1993. The SEBI (Mutual Fund) Regulations 1993 were substituted by a more comprehensive and revised Mutual Fund Regulations in 1996. The industry now functions under the SEBI (Mutual Fund) Regulations 1996.

Fourth Phase (2003 onwards)

In February 2003, following the repeal of UTI Act, 1963 UTI was bifurcated into two separate entities. One is the Specified undertaking of the UTI with assets under management of Rs. 29835 crores as at the end of January 2003. The second is the UTI Mutual Fund Ltd, sponsored by SBI, PNB, BOB and LIC. It is registered with SEBI and functions under the Mutual Fund Regulations.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

De Bondt and Thaler (1985) during the process of investigating the possible psychological basis for investor behaviour, argue that mean reversion in stock prices is an evidence of investor over reaction where investors over emphasize recent firm performance in forming future expectations.

Goetzman (1997) states that there is evidence that investor psychology affect fund/scheme selection and switching.

Ippolito (1992) says that fund selection by investors is based on past performance of the funds and money flows into winning funds more rapidly than they flow out of losing funds.

Madhusudhan V Jambodekar (1996) in his study states that among other things that income schemes and open ended schemes are more preferred than growth schemes and close ended schemes during the then prevalent market conditions.

Investors look for safety of principal, liquidity, and capital appreciation in the order of importance.

Sujit Sikidar & Amrit Pal Singh (1996) carried out a survey of the investors of the North Eastern region, which revealed that the salaried and self employed formed the major investors in mutual fund primarily due to tax concessions. UTI and SBI schemes were popular in that part of the country then and other funds had not proved to be a big hit during the time when survey was done.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. The present study has been undertaken to examine the issues and challenges to be addressed by means of Mutual Funds.

This paper aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To highlight the various types of mutual funds;
- To highlight the importance of investing in mutual funds in today' emerging financial market;
- To highlight the various factors influencing the selection of mutual funds by retail investors;

Area of Study

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However, opinion of officers/managers of various banks and as well as financial/investment planners in Moradabad and Jaipur districts of Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan respectively has been taken about the investment in mutual funds. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on mutual funds.

I have used qualitative research techniques as focus group discussion with respect to mutual funds investments. Our focus group discussion was based on some experts of financial and investment planning in Moradabad and Jaipur districts. The discussions were based on key analysis of investment with emphasis on factors affecting the selection of mutual funds investments.

IMPORTANCE OF MUTUAL FUNDS

Mutual funds have come as a much needed help to small investors who face a lot of problems in the share market, limited resources, lack of professional advice, lack of information, etc. It is a special type of institutional device or an investment vehicle through which the investors pool their savings which are to be invested under the guidance of a team of experts in wide variety of portfolios of corporate securities in such a way so as to minimize risk, while ensuring safety and steady return on investment. Now days, mutual fund is gaining attraction due to the following reasons:

- 1) The need and scope of mutual fund operation has increased tremendously due to the emphasis on

increase in domestic savings of investors and improvement in deployment of investment through markets. The reforms in the financial sector were undertaken to tap the vast potential of domestic savings and channelise them for profitable investments. Mutual funds are the best for this purpose.

- 2) Mutual funds set up by financial institutions enjoy tax benefits. Mutual funds do not deduct tax at source from dividends paid to investors. This is the most important advantage the mutual fund industry enjoys in India.
- 3) As mutual funds creates awareness among urban and rural middle class people about the benefits of investment in capital market, through profitable and safe avenues, mutual fund could be able to make up a large amount of the surplus funds available with these people.
- 4) Mutual funds invest funds in different companies of different sectors of industries with the result that the risks get diversified. An individual investor with limited means cannot do so.
- 5) Because of tax benefits, better portfolio management and low cost of transactions, mutual funds are able to earn more, and benefits of these are passed on to the investors.
- 6) Dividends and capital gains are reinvested automatically in mutual funds and hence are not fritted away. The automatic reinvestment feature of a mutual fund is a form of forced saving and can make a big difference in the long run.
- 7) Retail investors buy units of mutual funds which in turn purchase securities of companies, this way mutual funds channelize small savings of lakhs of retail investors in trade and industry. This results in the development of a country's economy as a whole. To attract investors mutual funds offer different kinds of schemes to them.
- 8) Mutual funds get preferential treatment in allotment of shares. In case of initial public offering by good companies the chances of individual investors getting allotment are scanty but mutual funds are assured of preferential allotment the benefit of which naturally passes on to the unit holders.
- 9) When and in which companies the funds should be invested is decided by a team of professional portfolio managers who posses specialized knowledge and experience in this field. They keep on doing research about investment avenues. Due to complex nature of the securities market, small investors can not do this work efficiently.
- 10) The mutual fund attracts foreign capital flow in the country and secures profitable investment avenues abroad for domestic savings through the opening of off shore funds in various foreign investors. Lastly, another notable thing is that mutual funds are

controlled and regulated by SEBI and hence are considered safe.

Due to all these benefits the importance of mutual funds has been increasing.

SHORTCOMINGS OF MUTUAL FUNDS

Mutual funds, however, are not unmixed blessings. They too have their shortcomings. They restrict investment opportunities to the investors. They suffer from infrequent trading and restricted liquidity. Sometimes, redemption may take long time or may be inconvenient or confusing. It may also require payment of some redemption fee. NAV may sometimes go below the cost of investment because of the fall in market prices of the securities. High cost of management of the funds is to be shared by the investors and their return on investments may be reduced.

LIMITATIONS OF MUTUAL FUNDS

There are certain limitations in investing in mutual funds such as:

- *Wrong investment:* It is not always possible for mutual fund managers to choose the right type of securities to invest the funds. Sometimes decision in choosing the right securities for the purpose of investment may go wrong, which may result in the reduction in the Net Asset Value of the mutual fund. In reality, no fund manager can always make correct decision.
- *Market risks:* There are so many risks which are not possible to foresee. Market prices are subject to fluctuations which are beyond the control of mutual funds' managers. The market risks cannot be altogether avoided or controlled.
- *Business risks:* mutual fund managers invest in the number of shares of different companies. Some companies may fail because of changing and dynamic circumstances. Some companies may not perform well or even suffer losses. Mutual funds may not foresee these risks to full extent.
- *Political risks:* The political party which came into power has its own philosophy about the business and commerce. Some may go for globalization and liberalization, some may go for protectionism, some may go for privatization, etc. The mutual fund managers may not be able to foresee these types of political risks.

TYPES OF MUTUAL FUNDS

Mutual funds offer different schemes to meet varied needs of investors. Some schemes offer regular income, some offer a promise of capital appreciation, some offer greater liquidity. Investors can choose the scheme suited to their needs. We can classify the mutual funds under the following sub-headings:

(1) On the basis of Entry and Exit:

- *Open Ended Mutual Funds:* These funds operate throughout the year. There is no opening or closing dates for investment in these funds. An investor can enter the scheme at any point of time and withdraw at any point of time. The purchase price or repurchase price are declared on the basis of NAV of the plan.
- *Close Ended Mutual Fund:* These funds are open for a specified period of time. The number of units to be issued and its duration is determined in advance. Once the subscription reaches the predetermined level no more investors can be admitted in the scheme. After the expiry of fixed period all the securities are sold out and the proceeds are distributed among unit holders of the scheme on the basis of units held by them.

(2) On the basis of Ownership:

- *Public Sector Mutual Funds:* The only public sector mutual fund was UTI established in 1964. It was in 1987 when the second public sector mutual fund was established by the State Bank of India. These funds are sponsored by any public sector undertaking. Major share of its paid up capital is subscribed by the sponsoring undertaking. CAN Bank Mutual Fund, PNB Mutual Fund, LIC Mutual Fund, BOB Mutual Fund etc are some of the funds under public sector.
- *Private Sector Mutual Funds:* The Central Government permitted on February 14, 1992 the private sector mutual funds to come up. Several private industrial enterprises sponsored mutual funds were established. Tata Mutual Fund, Birla Mutual Fund, Escorts Mutual Fund, etc are some of the private sector mutual funds.

(3) On the basis of income and investment pattern:

- *Income Funds:* In such funds the amount is invested in safe and income earning instruments like public deposits, bonds, etc. Investors are assured of regular income which may be paid on monthly, quarterly or half yearly basis.
- *Growth Funds:* These funds aim at capital appreciation for wealth maximization. Such funds fulfill expectations of those investors who want that their capital to be appreciated when they leave the plan. They do not care for regular income.
- *Balance Funds:* Such funds strike a balance between income and growth schemes. They fund managers of such funds invest in somewhat equal proportion in high growth equity and safe debt instruments. These funds have twin objectives; one is to provide regular income and second to have capital appreciation.
- *Equity Linked Saving Scheme:* This is a diversified mutual fund in which fund manager invests in various companies from various industry so risk factor is low. Also in India there is a tax benefit in investing in ELSS. These funds have a lock in period of three

years but the return is better and plus you will get tax benefits.

- *Index Funds:* Index funds replicate the portfolio of a particular index such as the BSE Sensitive Index, S&P NSE 50 indices (Nifty), etc. These schemes invest in the securities in the same weightage, comprising of an index. NAVs of such schemes would rise or fall in accordance with rise or fall in the index, though not exactly by the same percentage due to some factors known as "tracking error" in technical terms.
- *Sector Specific Funds:* These funds invest in securities of only those sectors or industries as specified in the offer documents for eg. Pharmaceuticals, software, fast moving consumer goods, petroleum, etc. the returns in these funds are dependent on the performance of the respective sectors/industries. While these funds may give higher returns, they are more risky compared to diversified funds.
- *Tax Saving Funds:* These funds are basically growth oriented schemes encashable after three to five years and attract those investors who want relief in income tax under section 80C of Income Tax Act, 1961
- *Money Market Mutual Funds:* Such funds invest in highly liquid and safe securities like commercial papers (CPs), treasury bills, bankers' acceptances, certificate of deposits, etc. All these are money market, i.e. short term instruments.
- *Stock Funds:* These funds invest in shares of corporate sector. Investment can be shifted from blue chip company to newly established company.
- *Bond Funds:* These funds invest in bonds only. It provides fixed and regular income.
- *Gilt Funds:* These funds invest exclusively in government securities. Government securities have no default risk. NAV of these schemes also fluctuate due to change in interest rates and other economic factors as is the case with income or debt oriented schemes
- *Small-Cap, Mid-Cap and Large-Cap Funds:* In stock market companies are divided into many groups according to their market capitalization like large-cap, mid-cap and small-cap companies. Market capitalization is one way of measuring the size of the company and is decided by the number of shares in the market and value per share. Mutual funds are also categorized like this based on the share they hold.

(4) On the basis of location:

- *Domestic Funds:* These funds operate in domestic limits only. To say, funds raising money within the territories of India
- *Off shore Funds:* Such funds are meant for non-resident investors i.e. the sources of funds are obtained from abroad. Such funds help in flow of

funds across different countries. These funds are subject to currency exchange rate risks and risks involved in investing in other countries. "India Fund", India growth fund" floated by UTI in UK and USA are examples of these funds.

MAIN MUTUAL FUNDS OPERATING IN INDIA

ABN Amro	AIG Global Invt.
Alliance capital	Birla Sunlife
Bank of Baroda	Benchmark
Canbank	DBS Cholamandalam
Deutsche	DSP Merrill Lynch
Escorts	Fidelity
Franklin Templeton	GIC
HDFC	HSBS
ICICI Prudential	ING Vysya
JM Financial	JP Morgan Stanley
Kotak Mahindra	LIC
Lotus India	Optimix
PNB	Principal
Quantum	Reliance
SBI	Standard Chartered
Sundaram BNP Paribas	Sahara India
Tata	Taurus
UTI	

All these funds have various types of schemes.

FUTURE PROSPECTS OF MUTUAL FUNDS

Mutual fund industry has bright prospects in India. In recent year rates of interest on fixed deposits have come down at fast rate and investors have started thinking of other avenues like investment in mutual funds which could bring them higher returns with safety.

Mutual funds in India are giving to their investors fairly good returns. The government is also encouraging mutual funds by granting tax deductions to the people investing in them. Growth in gross domestic savings and increasing equity cult in the country along with desire in the people to earn from savings has led to the rapid growth of mutual funds. Savings pattern of people has also changed from bank deposits to mutual funds. People have started looking for well managed mutual funds to accumulate more wealth over the years.

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE SELECTION OF MUTUAL FUND/SCHEME BY RETAIL INVESTORS

In financial markets expectations of the investors play a vital role. They influence the price of the securities; the volume traded and determines quite a lot of things in actual practice. These expectations of the investors are influenced by their perception and humans generally relate perception to action. The beliefs and actions of many investors are influenced by the dissonance effect and endowment effect.

- *Dissonance Effect*: The tendency to adjust beliefs to justify past actions is a psychological phenomenon termed as Cognitive Dissonance. There are lots of evidences of the prevalence of such a psychological state among

mutual fund investors in India. To say, UTI has glorious past and had always been perceived as a safe, high yield investment vehicle. Many UTI investors had justified their beliefs by staying invested in UTI schemes even after July, 2001 episode.

- *Endowment Effect*: Endowment effect states that people are more likely to believe that something they own is better than something they do not own. We also have lots of evidences of this effect among mutual fund investors, for how also can be explain the reason for the existence of many poor performing funds without investors staying invested with them?

An investor takes into account various factors while deciding about buying of a mutual fund. These ranges of factors begin with investor perception, the promised return and to the attractiveness of the offer.

The various key factors of a mutual fund product are mentioned herein below:

- *The core product*: Awareness of the attribute of the product, hassle free trading, exclusively for small investors, ownership of the product, technology, brand name and lock in period.
- *Investors' expectation*: Performance of the fund, safety, regular income, liquidity, benefit of tax deduction.
- *Service behaviour*: Transparency, service behaviours and delivery schedule.
- *Persuasive promotion*: Sponsor reputation, suggestions or publicity from friends or relatives, recommendations from agents or brokers, advertisements.
- *Investor confidence*: performance, assured return and degree of capital appreciation.

The investors look for safety first in mutual fund products followed by good returns, tax benefits, capital appreciation and liquidity. An investor takes into account various factors while deciding about buying of a mutual fund. These ranges of factors begin with investor perception, the promised return and to the attractiveness of the offer. The various factors which influence the selection of mutual fund /scheme by retail investors are mentioned herein below:

- 1) *Intrinsic Qualities of the Product*: It has been observed that the investors are basically influenced by the intrinsic qualities of the product followed by efficient portfolio management and general image of the fund/scheme in their selection of fund schemes. The intrinsic qualities of the product include withdrawal/exit facility, favorable rating, tax benefits, entry/exit load, innovativeness of the scheme, etc. The portfolio management includes performance record, portfolio of investment, etc. The general image of the fund includes reputation and brand name of the sponsor.
- 2) *Fund Management Team*: A critical component that determines performance of a mutual fund is the fund manager and his/her team. Finally it is their skills

- which are responsible in the decisions made regarding investing. The investors have to look at both aspects – ‘Fund Manager’ and ‘The Team’ behind him/her. If the fund manager has been around for a while, by looking at past performance we can get some idea about his/her abilities. Even though the fund manager is the key decision maker and is finally responsible for the fund performance, his/her team too is important. To this end the process followed in short listing and selecting investment opportunities is important.
- 3) *Infrastructural Facilities of The Sponsor*: The infrastructural facilities of the sponsor and the reputation enjoyed by the sponsor influence the investors in selecting the schemes of the mutual fund. The infrastructure facilities include agency network, research wing and expertise in money management, etc. The reputation of the sponsor includes ability of the sponsor to offer a range of schemes, brand name of the sponsor, etc.
 - 4) *Scheme Philosophy*: Whenever a mutual fund scheme is launched there is specific mandate (philosophy of investing) based on which investing is done by that mutual fund. This mandate outlines the debt-equity mix and the type of instruments that the fund would invest. For example, the prospectus of a mutual fund will always mention the stock universe that fund invests in viz, large cap, mid cap, small cap, sector funds, etc.
 - 5) *Low Interest Rates*: The good performance of many growth schemes and the low interest rates has attracted the retail investors in various growth schemes.
 - 6) *Disclosure by the Fund*: The retail investors are influenced by the extent and quality of disclosure of information subsequent to their investment regarding disclosure of (a) Net Asset Value, (b) portfolio of investment, (c) deviation of investment from the stated objectives, (d) Scheme’s investment on every trading day, (e) method and periodicity of the schemes sales and repurchases in the offer documents, and (f) investment objectives, methods and periodicity of valuation in advertisements.
 - 7) *Technology*: Technology adopted by various mutual fund companies also affects the decision in selecting the scheme of mutual funds. Technology has seen a phenomenal growth in financial services industry in the last few years. A number of financial institutions and intermediaries have started taking concrete initiatives towards offering comprehensive online services to the mutual fund investors. Today, many individual investors make extensive use of internet for investment research and their number is increasing day by day. By visiting various web sites, they can now see fund’s portfolio, get stock quotes, and engage in e-trading.
 - 8) *Own Decision*: Many times it has been seen that investors prefer to make their own decision in the selection of schemes, inspite of their lack of expert knowledge about the market environment.
 - 9) *Grievance Redressal Machinery*: The existence of mutual fund investors’ grievance redressal machinery creates confidence in the minds of the retail investors. The retail investors prefer those schemes/mutual funds which have proper grievance redressal machinery, so that if any problem arises or investors have some doubt or confusion they may contact the concerned mutual fund office for solving the problem.
 - 10) *Fringe Benefits*: The various fringe benefits provided by mutual fund companies also influence the selection of schemes by the retail investors. The fringe benefits include free insurance, tax benefits, free credit card, loans on collateral security, and the like.
- Thus, we can say that while selecting any one of the schemes of the mutual fund, the investor must bear in mind his age and the capacity to bear risk. Investor must also ensure that the management of the fund has a market reputation of being more transparent and the perception of an honest and efficient management. Investor must also examine the consistency in the performance and the after sales services of the mutual fund.
- SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT IN THE FUNCTIONING OF MUTUAL FUNDS**
- The following suggestions for improving the functioning of mutual funds and to create confidence in the minds of the investors are noteworthy:
- 1) Regulation of mutual funds is necessary to protect the interest of the investors but over-regulation may prove to be counterproductive.
 - 2) Mutual funds are made by investors and investors interest ought to be paramount by setting standard of behaviors and efficiency through self regulation and professionalism;
 - 3) A wiser balance be maintained between liquidity and return;
 - 4) Cost of management of the fund should be kept as low as possible;
 - 5) Fund managers may be educated in business ethics;
 - 6) SEBI should avoid undue delay in decision-making and strictly curb unethical practices;
 - 7) Grievance Redressal Machinery should be established by the mutual fund companies to redress the complaints of the investors;
 - 8) Proper disclosure of information mechanism should be maintained so that investors know what risk they are taking by investing in funds;
 - 9) Mutual funds need to take advantage of modern technology like computer and tele-communications to render service to the investors;

- 10) Greater transparency should be brought about to gain investors' confidence;
- 11) Fund managers must be honest, highly qualified and experienced;
- 12) As the investors are not willing to invest in mutual fund unless a minimum return is assured, it is very essential to create in the mind of the investors that mutual funds are market instruments and associated with market risk hence mutual fund could not offer guaranteed income.

IV. CONCLUSION

Government has introduced several regulations for the safety of the interests of the investors. RBI, SEBI and the Government are continuously working in this direction and have laid down several guidelines for the safety of small investors, such as separate norms have prescribed for minimum corpus of various kinds of funds, their investment patterns, distribution of profits, etc.

Over the period, fund monitoring and management have improved. Greater transparency is helping the mutual funds to gain more confidence of the investors and change in their perception. Growing competition and increasing experience is helping the mutual funds to come out with new innovative schemes from cradle to retirement. Effective marketing and distribution strategies are not only increasing the awareness of the benefits of mutual funds amongst the investors, but also securing a positive response to the various schemes.

Mutual funds in India have tremendous potential. Their success will, however, depend upon their efficient and honest management and the independence of relationship between Sponsors, Asset Management Company, Trustee Company, Custodian and Fund Manager. Each constituent must take independent and professional decision in the best interest of the investors. Fund managers must be honest, highly qualified and experienced. Their decision must be based on investment and market research. Transparency and integrity in decision-making must be strictly observed to ensure success of the mutual fund. Improved information disclosures and investors awareness will certainly advance the cause of the investors towards efficient management of the fund.

REFERENCES

- [1] Agarwal, G. D. 1992. "Mutual Funds and Investors Interest", Chartered Secretary, Vol 22, No. 1.
- [2] Anagol, Malati & Katoli, Raghavendra. "Mutual Funds: Just five year old and ready to run at a gallop", Economic Times, Feb. 27, 1992.
- [3] Atmaramani, 1995. "SEBI Regulations-A Case for level playing field", Analyst.
- [4] Chakrabarti Anjan & Rungta Harsh, 2000. "Mutual Funds Industry in India: An indepth look into the problems of credibility, Risk and Brand", The ICAFI Journal of Applied Finance, Vol 16, No. 2.
- [5] Chandra, Prasanna. "The Investment Game" Tata McGraw Hill Publishing, New Delhi.
- [6] Dave, S. A. "Mutual Funds: Growth and Development". The Journal of the Indian Institute of Bankers, Jn March, 1992.
- [7] De Bondtt, & Thaler R., 1985. "Does the stock market over react?" Journal of Finance.
- [8] De, Mainak. "Mutual Funds and Institutions-paying to a different tune", Economic Times, June 15, 1991.
- [9] Festinger, L. 1957. "A theory of Cognitive Dissonance" Stanford University Press, Standord.
- [10] Goetzman, W. N. 1997. "Cognitive Dissonance and Mutual Fund Investors", The Journal of Financial Research 20, Summer 1997.
- [11] Gupta, L. C. 1994. "Mutual Funds and Assets Preference" Society for Capital Market Research and Development, Delhi.
- [12] Ippolito, R. 1992. "Consumer reaction to measures of poor quality: Evidence from Mutual Funds" Journal of Law and Economics.
- [13] Madhusudan V. Jambodekar, 1996. "Marketing Strategies of Mutual Funds – Current Practices and Future Directions", Working Paper, UTI – IIMB Centre for Capital Markets Education and Research, Bangalore.
- [14] Panda T. K. & Tripathy N. P. "Customer Orientation in Designing Mutual Fund Products-An Analytical Approach to Indian Market Preferences".
- [15] Rajeshwari, T. R. "An Empirical Study on Factors Influencing the Mutual Fund/Scheme Selection by Retail Investors".
- [16] Raja Rajan, 1998. "Investment size based segmentation of individual investors", Management Researcher.
- [17] Ramola, K. S. "Mutual Fund and the Indian Capital Market" Yojana, Vol. 36, No. 11, June 30, 1992
- [18] Sahai, I. M., "Financial Market Operations". Sahitya Bhawan Publishers and Distributors (P) Ltd. Agra.
- [19] Sarkar, A. K., 1991. "Mutual Funds in India: Emerging Trends", Management Accountant, Vol. 26 No. 3.
- [20] Shukla, Sharad. "Mutual Funds: Past performance is no indicator of the future" Economic Times, June 15, 1991.
- [21] Sujit Sikidar and Amrit Pal Singh, 1996. "Financial Services: Investment in Equity and Mutual Funds-A Behavioural Study". Management of Financial Services, Deep and Deep Publications, New Delhi.
- [22] Srinivasan Ajay, 1999. "Mutual Funds: The New Era", Chartered Secretary.
- [23] Tripathy, N. P. 1996. "Mutual Fund In India: A Financial Service in Capital Market". Finance India, Vol. X, No. 1 March 1996.
- [24] Verma, J. C. "Manual of Merchant Banking: Concepts, Practices & Procedures. Bharat Law House, New Delhi..
- [25] Vidhya Shankar, S. 1990. "Mutual Funds-Emerging Trends in India", Chartered Secretary, Vol. 20, No. 8.
- [26] Vyas, B. A. "Mutual Funds-Boon to the Common Investors" Fortune India, July 16, 1990.
- [27] Yasaswy, N. J. "Personal Investment and Tax Planning Year Book". Vision Books, New Delhi.
- [28] Economic Times
- [29] Financial Express
- [30] Times of India
- [31] Yojana